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Rethinking Human–Computer Relations In New Critical And Literary Contexts: Can The Digital Experience Of Internet of Things (IOTs) Be Enriched?

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Abstract

This paper investigated human–robot interaction as a research field that aims to enrich the user experience and the consumer market. Starting with the functionalist approach to the field based on narrow technologism perspectives, the paper pointed out that it is necessary to adopt a method that goes beyond the limited technology orientation. Drawing insights from Aristotle’s theory of friendship on social ontology, Winner’s theory of interaction with computers and robots, and social exchange theory, it proposed critical interdisciplinarity as the best approach to artificial intelligence, computer science, cognitivism and engineering.

It argued that the major challenge of the field is to be truly open-ended, innovative and capable of breaking new frontiers. From this light, it suggested priority should be given to new issues such as the sociality between robots and humans, the question of social acceptance, intimacy with robots, relationships and perception of benefits, the interface of humans and technology and the role of the enactive in cognitive science. In addition, the researcher should take into consideration the problematic of co-habitation, the morality and rights of/ rights over robots, discussions about perceptions of and physical responses to intimacy with robots, the fear of ‘Deleuzian bodies’ and the need for coordination.

Keywords

Human–robot interaction, critical contexts, IOTs, social acceptance of relationship, modeling of gender and love, Deleuzian bodies, enactivism, consumer/user experience

1.0 Introduction

Humanity is now witnessing the emergence of human-robot interaction as a very challenging field of research dealing with the naturalization of interaction, play, work and capabilities of robots. The field is already impacting user experiences and the consumer market but for this to be sustainable, it is important that it should embrace a critical stance beyond functionalism. Interdisciplinarity can be an appropriate answer with different viewpoints, and methodologies, a wider perspective that that opens up new directions, innovative views and challenging frontiers that lead to richer user experience and that is sensitive to the consumer market.

However, the activities of robots and humans have to be coordinated and temporalized. The real challenges go beyond engineering to embrace social, psychological and communicative viewpoints. The interdisciplinary should leverage the ‘human’ side in the loop of the human-robot interaction.

2.0 2.0 Related works

Research effort in computer and robotic technologies and their relations and interactions with humans strives to generate content that can enrich consumer/user experience. However, these studies have been dominated by narrow functionalist readings of the current situation of these phenomena on human-robot and computer interaction and relations. Narrow functionalist research investigates,

3.0 2.1 Situated utterance generation

For example, situated utterance generation has been researched in human-robot interaction [1]. In conjunction with this angling, the authors tried to inquire to see how joint attention can be achieved because a human must have joint attention with a computer or a robot in order to identify the object indicated by a situated utterance description generated.

2.2 Co-presence, spatial relations and embodied interaction

According to a study by a number of scholars [2], there are two basic features of the command and control situation of service robots. They draw attention to spatial distances and orientation of a robot as far as a

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human user is concerned in an experimental setting. A similar study [3] proposes a human-robot interaction system that learns the model for spatial prepositions and the model for object recognition. The system proposes grounds upon which the significance of an input sentence can be evaluated in the light of visual percepts in a robot's sensors.

2.3 Robots at home

The study [4] may draw attention to the system itself that can interact with the user and points out the possibilities for constructing this class of robots

2.4 The linguistic human-robot interaction

Some studies [5] are designed to facilitate spontaneous and efficient spatial reference to objects in multiple human-robot interaction contexts. They focus on the iterative, empirically grounded design of a robotic system that deploys a computational model for identifying objects.

2.5 Urban search and rescue disaster response

This study [6] considers USAR robot operator interactions in the context of team members in order to capture observable indicators. It suggests that by exploring dyad, form, and content, one can identify the team members that interact and what they are doing.

2.6 Attitudes toward robots

Users are not deceived by a robotic dog; rather, they are conscious that the dog is a robot and their intention is a peripheral one of enjoying interactions with them [7]. Similarly, [8] investigates psychological factors, which stop humans from effective interaction with robots. The authors make an international comparison of negative attitudes toward robots and find out their relationships with behaviours. They prompt respondents for validity confirmation.

2.7 Learning in human robot interactions

The different types of interfaces that enable humans to control, direct or interact are researched with the focus being on learning in human robot interactions [9]. The tasks and their complexity that a robot has to learn is investigated via very tight human-robot interaction methods.

2.8 Communication perspectives

The paper [10] may investigate tasks from ambiguous demonstrations or the factors that facilitate human-robot communication with an emphasis on overall impression and appreciation of the interaction.

2.9 Social presence

It was observed [11] that users feel an intense sense of social presence when interacting with a robot. The social agent is mediated by the user's feeling that a certain social presence is obvious during the interaction. The need to prioritize a touch-input capability and to analyze the impact of loneliness during human-robot interaction is raised.

2.10 Efficiency and cognitive interaction

A human who is remote cannot interact directly with the world but must do so through a robot; hence the need to prioritize cognitive information processing, given that interaction with the world must adopt a mental model [12]

2.11 The habituation effect in human-robot interaction

This study [13] investigates the employment of robots to interact with autistic patients and discovers that during weeks 1 and 2, there is a certain distance kept between robot and user, but from week 5, participants start to allow the robot to approach closer compared to weeks 1 and 2.

2.12 Psychological benchmarks

These benchmarks have been identified to include intuitions, individualism, socialization, moral underpinnings and so on [14].

2.13 Time and interaction

It was observed [15] that there was a continuous accumulation interaction time of user A with the robot and the same result was obtained with respect to the time that users A and B simultaneously interact with the robot

2.14 Phenomenology and relations

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This paper [16] observes that interaction with robots is never smooth because any relation like a human-robot relation can change and does change. There are lots of differences between users and this impacts how they interact with robots.

2.15 Application in the industrial sector

This paper [17] considers issues concerning human-robot interaction in the industrial sector and discusses the approach to industrial robotics, especially, the impoverished human-robot interaction

2.16 Human and robotic personality traits

A new area of research is the identification of links intersecting user personality and attributed robot personality [18]. This study inquires into human and robot personality features as continuation of a human-robot interaction trial.

3.0 Methods and materials

This paper deploys insights from the social exchange theory. The theory predicts that human beings start off relationships on the basis of benefits (Dagger 2011 [19], Sweeney and Webb 2007 [20]) trust (Ko and SeungUk 2014 [21]), justice (Ko and SeungUk 2014 [21]), safety (Hofmann and Morgeson 1999 [22]), intentions and satisfactions (Shiau and Luo 2012 [23]) and other motivations (Bendapudi and Leonard 1997 [24]) that they derive from them. If such benefits and trust are absent or are not felt consistently, then it is unlikely that a relationship would be established.

Winner (2010) [25] uses Wittgenstein to argue that when we interact with computers and robots, we take with us highly structured anticipation about entities that appear to participate in forms of life and associated games that are part of human culture. Whenever one interacts with humanoid robots, what matters to the interactive form is not the physical properties of the robots but the relation between their appearance and the human forms of life, namely, human biology, human social life and human culture. Acceptance of robots would depend on whether they fit with a particular form of life. Since forms of life differ within different cultures, interactions with and attitudes toward robots will also differ. Drawing insights from Karl Marx *The German ideology*, while rejecting his determinism, Wilson reads that a mode of production is a mode of life. Consequently, by shaping material objects, we also change ourselves. An important dimension of Marxist thinking is the stress on life-processes in relation to technology. Marxist materialism is also a form of naturalism and a transcendental ground marked by thought and language. The winner demonstrates that both Marx and Wittgenstein had a relational view in which both the technological and the human, the material and the social had a firm connection. Following Heidegger's and Wittgenstein's transcendentalist approach, technology is a condition of *possibility* for human society and culture in as much as it is a condition of possibility for what can be said about artificial and natural entities.

The paper also draws from a theory of friendship in which Aristotle raises the issue of social ontology. This will enable this paper to deploy it to assess the real value of social robotics and emerging social technologies (Elder 2018) [26].

4.0 Hypothesis

This paper is premised on the hypothesis that in order to enrich consumer/user experience, research effort needs to consider the 'bigger picture' of interactions and relations between humans, computers and robots by expanding the narrow focus on machines and incorporating the critical perspectives of humanity in context.

5.0 Sociality between robots and humans

The concept of 'social robot' was created by Cynthia Breazeal (2002) [27], Kerstin Dautenhahn and Aude Billard (Billard and Dautenhahn 1997) [28] to design and develop robots with capabilities to interact with human beings at the social level. However, when it comes to multirobot systems, for example, sociality between robots is not part of the field of studies. The strong approach to social robotics aims to construct robots with capabilities to display emotional and social behaviour. The weak approach only inquires into how robots can imitate emotional and social behaviour. Consequently, social robotics has been faced with a very serious challenge of how to draw resources from other disciplines beyond its computer science and engineering

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foundations. It is important that social robots should exhibit human-social qualities such as the development of personality, the employment of natural cues, learning, the cultivation of personality, the achievement of dialogue, the articulation of emotions, and the development of social competences (Fong et al. 2003 [29], Breazeal 2002 [27], Weber 2005 [30]). As a result, the past few years have been marked by attempts to move the field from its traditional conception of social robotics to a more performative one under the name of human-robot interaction.

The severely restricted behaviour and cognitive abilities of today's robots have been a major concern for robot scientists in this field, who decided to seek a solution to the problem by modeling out a human-robot relation as caregiver-infant relation. With the increasing inclination towards adopting knowledge from human-computer interaction, the field of social robotics is now being substituted by human-robot interaction. The idea behind this 'solution' of introducing a robot as a young child or a baby was to 'naturalize' these restrictions. A new challenge is posed at this level though. A lot of precautions should be taken here because the idea that the realization and vision of social artefacts can be integrated into research on software agents and robotics raises other questions. For example, in these social artefacts, whose and what understanding of sociality and emotionality is being realized? Will the critical, feminist perspective (that influences the consumer market and user experience through its ICT gender politics) accept that it is desirable to develop 'emotional artefacts' that humans are supposed to empathize with? When models of artefacts are infantilized, is it from the perspective of babies or from that of adults who have their own cultural conception of what a baby needs, feels, etc.

Human-robot relations and interaction are now emerging as a cross-disciplinary field of studies that resides at the intersection of artificial intelligence, robotics, ethology, interaction design, cognitive science, biology, and developmental psychology. In addition to the above-mentioned disciplines, it would be necessary to incorporate into the discipline of human-robot interaction field, sociology, pedagogy, science and technology studies, and philosophy as part of the field. This incorporation would enrich the human-robot interaction research programmes that aim to investigate how humans perceive robotic systems, the designing of robotics as functional systems, zoomorphs or anthropomorphs, the issue of user friendliness, ethical concerns and so forth.

6.0 The question of social acceptance

The challenge for robot designers is how to work toward achieving success in the social acceptance of human-robot interaction. Already, the affect of minimal social cues from consumer robots such as Pleo, My Real Baby, Fubies, Tamagotchi, and AIBO, shows that the level of perception and acceptance of robots has shifted spectacularly over the decades. For example, young children are already ascribing social robots with a category of 'being' which is situated between 'alive' and 'not alive,' and known as a 'sort of alive' (Kidd, Cory D., and Cynthia Breazeal 2007 [31], Feil-Seifer, David, Kristine Skinner, and Maja J. Matarić, 2007 [32]). The child of today still feels compelled to classify robots, like the child of two decades ago, when they came into confrontation with intelligent machines. But in addition to the above problem, the urge to classify is compounded by the desire to nurture and be nurtured by relational artefacts. There is also the problem of emotional attachments. Designers of robots like Breazeal feel attached to their robots. However, this capability of robots to provide a good 'fake' or 'deception' shows that the interaction of robots and vulnerable people like the elderly and children is ethically problematical. There is a need for a new language and sets of words that perfectly capture the shifting ontological status of the robotic other.

A new culture has now emerged in which the borders between animate and non-animate has eroded in significant ways. The question is: can this new technology truly enrich the lives of children, adults and elderly persons? What paradigms can be deployed to respond to serious preoccupations with issues like the appropriateness of love relationships between humans and robots? What paradigm can be employed to manage anthropomorphism and evaluate authenticity in robots? There is a need for a new theory of machines, a methodological framework that would enable us to think about the hybrid configurations of technology and culture, of humans and robots, and the actor network theory can be one of the serious models for such a perspective.

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7.0 Intimacy with robots

A major point of challenge for the human-robot interaction project is the question of intimacy. Researchers are taking measures to meet the challenges that robots are posing, namely, using their multiple capabilities to stimulate the senses of humans. To what degree do humans comprehend and are willing to accept intimacy with robots? The way users *see* human-robot interaction has a certain degree of impact on how they comprehend intimacies with robots. If contact with robots is allowed to go on for the long term, the chances increase in terms of acceptance. This is so because human intimacy perception is not stagnant but will transform to accommodate new intimacy shades of meaning. The absence of consciousness about the potentials of robots can only lead to feelings of fear

8.0 Relationships and perception of benefits

From the viewpoint of interaction, humans actually commit to face-to-face communicative behaviour, whenever they see evidence of a social stimulus; however, the real challenge is at the level of the formation of relationships. From the results of the current research done, it is impossible to know whether humans form relationships with robots. From the research that has been carried out, there is ample evidence that humans express a will to belong (Baumeister and Leary 1995) [33]. Nevertheless, when it comes to relationships, it is a more complex matter even among humans themselves, speak less of between humans and robots. This complication stems from the fact that in order to materialize a relationship, it must be achieved by taking into account multiple variables at the level of the system. For example, humans would not enter into a relationship if they do not see benefits, such as health consequences or do not trust the system and feel safe with it.

An even greater challenge is how to establish rules for the human-agent/human interaction in such a way that it radically alienates from what human beings know and employ everyday.

9.0 Interfacing humans and technology

As robots play omnipresent roles in society, it should become easier for human individuals to employ and interact with it. We can also speculate that different classes of people in terms of gender, levels of income, educational levels, age, etc. should find that the robot appeals to them. However, the major challenge is how to interface properly human beings who are not trained with the robotic technology in such a way that enjoyability, efficiency and intuition are integrated.

In the field of human-computer interaction, a lot of findings are already evident about how people interact with computers. For example, evidence from research teams shows that computer critics, experts and ordinary people give treatments to computers in ways which are similar to how they treat other human beings (Klein, Ewan 2003 [34], Kallinen, Kari, and Niklas Ravaja 2007 [35], Heerink, Marcel, et al. 2010 [36], Moon 2003 [37], Garzon, Max H., and Tutoring Research Group 1999 [38], Goldie et al. 2011 [39]). They treat the computer with a touch of ‘politeness,’ refrain from criticizing it for fear that its ‘feelings’ may be hurt, side with the computer to play games with other human beings playing from another team, and feel good whenever they are praised by the computer. However, the point is that human beings offer this treatment at an unconscious level. They hardly agree that they are doing this and even strongly deny such a possibility even after experiments were carried out by the research teams. They believed that they treated computers as machiness rather than as people. The reason why people adopt the behaviour of treating computers as though they were human beings has to do with evolution (Reeves and Nash 1996 [40]). The human brain went into evolution in a universe where rich social behaviour was shown only by human beings and all objects perceived were seen as real physical objects. Consequently, anything that appeared like a real place or person appeared real (Ibid: 12 [40]). The human brain is now hard-wired with innate mechanisms to allow humans to interact in social ways with others who comport themselves socially.

Although the human brain has not undergone much change over a period of thousands of years, it has to deal with technology. So, whenever technology comports itself in ways that are judged to be socially competent, human beings summon their evolved social machinery to interact with it. Human beings spend more

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effort in order to inhibit their social machinery not to give machinery such treatment as machines. From what Reeves and Nash (1996) [40] present as a universal interface, one can hypothesize that human beings would accept technological efforts to promote human-technology relationships but on condition that the technological machinery is able to exhibit rich social comportment. Humanoid robots with similar morphology and sensing modalities are now well equipped to perform these acts. The priority has to go with the enrichment of the human style of social exchange in which robots participate. By displaying such competence, human beings will be able to work with them as if they were humans as well. Since human beings have shown expertise in social interaction, it should not be difficult to communicate with robots and this would, in turn, facilitate new forms of learning such as emulation, imitation and the teaching of new tasks.

The challenge, therefore, is not only to build robots, but to construct robots that are capable of learning like human beings. In this way, the environment of human learning would become one of the really autonomous robots. Such an environment would hold potential for a near human social interactivity capability because robots would be able to co-habit with people as part of a learning process with the potential to adapt to new social experiences, hone prediction intuitions, employ social cues and generate new skills. The potential is therefore evident for the commencement of a new form of human sociality designed as an infrastructure that would support the interface between a robot child caregiver and society. This human-robot relation should also be endowed with the capacity to learn (Scasselatti 2002 [41], Breazeal and Scassellati 2002 [42], Ibid 2002 [43], DiSalvo et al. 2002 [44], Scassellati 2007 [45], Fasel, Ian, et al. 2002 [46], Scholtz 2002 [47]).

10.0 The enactive in cognitive science

When Varela, Thompson and Rosch (1991) [48] published their work entitled *The embodied mind*, the term ‘enactive’ became fashionable in cognitive science. The use of the term also penetrated the fields of human computer interaction, consciousness studies and autonomous robotics. This term stressed the idea of the relation of co-determination between cognitive agents and the world, experience as an embodiment and the notion of autonomy. The term ‘enactive’ was an attempt to synthesize disapprovals over the computational paradigm, together with the articulation of a set of postulates to move the concept forward. Enactivism should be the by-word and guide for the advent of a new epoch in cognitive science and human-robot interaction; but, it is also clear that the employment of the term inheres a variety of complex meanings as one finds in associated terms like embodied, autonomous and dynamical. For example, the emerging perspective of embodied cognition holds that cognitive processes are profoundly ingrained in the body's interactions with the world. This viewpoint actually embodies certain claims, with some of them more controversial than other claims. Wilson (2002) [49] suggests six major claims, namely, that cognition is situated, time-pressured, for action, offline cognition is body based, people off-load cognitive work onto the environment and the environment is a part of the cognitive system. Therefore, the adoption of enactivism in human-robot interaction should proceed with caution as the term internalizes a number of ambiguities and nuances that are not straightforward.

Enactive synonymizes with active, physical, changing, and exchanging information with the environment, which are all properties a robot can claim. In order for enactive cognitive science to take off the ground, the original ideas of enactivism should be adopted partially or sublimated into other frameworks. Enactive proposals should cause progress for open-ended questions in cognitive science in such a way as to motivate higher-level cognition. The utilitarianism of enactive concepts is limited to the lower levels of human cognition. In this reform and not revolution interpretation, situated and engaged involvement with the environment is enough to depict how something navigates. However, this model does not tell us how one can travel from a given place to another. Enactivism concepts can also prevail in the development of complex skills such as controlling sensorimotor dependencies in the perception of visual objects (O'Regan and Noe 2011) [50]. But these are cognitively marginal skills; it is necessary to acquire another set of skills to account for the whole picture of performance. Enactivism also has its limitations and it would be right to see it as a framework to be developed and extended.

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Any research programme in human-robot interaction should resist the temptation to find definite solutions to problems because there would always be definitional issues. Thus, it is critical to adopt a spirit of engendering rather than one of a solution, to indicate horizons rather than boundaries. Many areas of performance in enactive cognitive science with potential applications in human-robot interaction still need to be developed such as in imagination, thinking, and interpretation of the comportment of other people or objects. In formulating questions and possible answers to enactivism, it is equally important to adopt a number of methods such as theory /experiment cycles, phenomenology, validation by construction and synthesis by minimal models.

11.0 Discussion

Human-robot interactions have been creating new possibilities for companionship with artificial machine intelligence. The more a robot displays qualities of human beings such as in terms of physical appearance, comportment and the ways it interacts with human beings, the more human beings can *accept* it and engage happily with it. But the prospect of robots becoming intimate with human beings is controversial because of the problematic of co-habitation. The challenge, therefore, is how to create robots that are not just instruments but exhibit qualities that mere tools do not possess such as thinking, anticipating, walking, compassioning and talking. Whatever the case, it will be very challenging for humans to *accept* robots as their intimate companions, even if they express a strong desire to make such a connection. There are also new questions that are emerging concerning the morality and rights of/ rights over robots. Therefore, it is necessary to invest in a lot of time in order to achieve an approximate level of communication that is similar to human-human interaction.

A platform should be created to facilitate discussions on perceptions and physical responses to intimacy with robots, physiological responses to human-robot interaction, etc. the long term goal of this conversation is to answer the critical question of how to deal with the question of preference for the concept of intimacy with robots. Physiological reactions may rate better for visual stimuli when the robot sings like a female; however, they may not rate well for haptic stimuli when it comes to touching the breasts or buttocks of a robot, for example. In David Levy's (2009) book *Love and sex with robots: The evolution of human-robot relationships* [51], the artificial intelligence expert maintains that what was once considered as mechanical and cold may soon emerge as an object of human desire and great companionship. He demonstrates how automata evolved and human interactions with technology transformed aspects of human relationships such as why people fall in love, form emotional connections to virtual pets and animals and speculates that these same attachments can expand to include romantic love for robots. In this regard, society's fixed ideas about the character of normal sex may change with the increasing sophistication of sexual technology. However, given that this is a real challenge area for technology, conversations should continue with new questions of scenarios and roles of robots like sexual partners, lovers, caregivers, other halves, domestic maids and so forth so as to develop the critical question of perception of and responsiveness to technology and psychology.

Robots, like social media, appeal to the human desire for social interactions; however, such an interaction comes with costs and risks of face-to-face human interaction. An even greater challenge is this: can robots offer human beings *real* friendship? It is necessary to continue the debate on the ontology of friendship. Possible research questions that would open up avenues to explore human-robot interaction would include definitions of friendship and its functionality, the factors that can harm it, its relationship to philosophical and ethical issues such as value, character, well-being, etc. The insights from these debates have to be applied to how robotic companions can be designed for market consumers like elderly persons, how therapeutic robots can be deployed to tutor mentally disabled children on social skills, and how companionate robots can be modelled for other needs in the consumer market. Although there is no doubt that there are real and measurable benefits for the designing of companionate robots, the debate on these forms of interaction has to be expanded to include the moral hazards that are inherent in robotic encounters. It is arguable that (like with social media video chats, text messaging, Snapchat and Facebook), human-robot interaction may either, on the one hand, trigger a

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deterioration of social connections, as an effect, or may, on the other hand, empower human society to sustain, develop and enrich human friendship in significant ways.

There is the greatest challenge that human-robot interaction may lead to what is called the emergence of ‘Deleuzian bodies’, that is, technological bodies that may come to dominate and even possibly destroy the human body from a physical, moral, social, cultural and spiritual perspective. Raising this issue is critical for the consumer market and for the enrichment of user experience because the market does not function in a sociological vacuum, but rather operates in a society of human beings who are satisfied with their needs. These needs are embedded in the physical, moral, social, cultural and spiritual perspectives. Consequently, precaution must be taken to ensure that research on human-robot interaction does not lead to a world of ‘Deleuzian bodies’ as narrated in Philip Dick’s (1968) *Do androids dream of electric sheep?* [52]. In this book which was made into a film ‘*Blade Runner*,’ the protagonist Rick, is tasked with identifying, hunting down and destroying illegal androids. With the development of very sophisticated models, programmed to pass screening tests - comprised of a Turing test and biometric lie detector – it becomes virtually impossible to make the distinction between robot and human beings. *Neuromancer* is authored by W. Gibson (1984) [53] and based on a world in which human beings are frightened by the prospect of being destroyed by very intelligent robotic programmes they created. Consequently, they work to stop the artificial intelligence programmes from assuming a totalitarian, autonomous and sentient control over humans. The Turing Police is charged with eliminating all programmes that allow full sentience and prosecute all humans who enable it.

Similarly, in the TV series *Battlestar Galactica*, cylons (i.e., androids) try to eliminate the whole of the human race that created them even though, from a biological perspective, they are not distinguishable from humans. By ‘wiring’ machine intelligence into human flesh, cylons in both *Battlestar Galactica* and *Do androids dream of electric sheep?* raise the issue of the definition of the human ‘body’. Thus, the question is no longer what happens when human intelligence is logged into the ‘body’ of a machine; rather, the fictional and critical question now is: what happens to the human race when machine intelligence finds its way into the ‘bodies’ of human beings? The answer to that question is the potential treachery of humanoid robots and the menace of artificial intelligence which are engendering anxieties because of possibilities of future indistinction between the human and the mechanical. Despite the fright that this prospect may cause from the technofantasy of cyberspace, the bathwater and the baby should not be thrown away. The reality (the baby) is that human beings have been marked by a strong desire – explainable by magical and Gnostic thinking, Christian reincarnation doctrines, other religious ideologies - to escape from the body and by a strong conviction that cybertechnology will make this to happen. The cyberspace imaginary is characterized by an investment in the perception that the body has material limitations and the idea of transcendence of the body (Davis 1994) [54].

12.0 Concluding remarks and outlook

Humanity is now at the dawn of the epoch of human-robot interaction because artificial intelligence, motion technologies and efficient/compact batteries are intersecting quickly than before, as a result, human-robot relations and interaction is becoming a growing field of research which is very challenging because it deals with how humans can interact, play and work with robots and also with how the capabilities of robots can best be optimized to work with humans. The major objective is to inquire into how the interaction and communication with robots can be ‘naturalized’ as much as possible. The field is already impacting on the economic domain of society as well as on the relationships humans have with machines and the way humans live in society. As an interdisciplinary field of research, it is very challenging because it has to deploy knowledge from various disciplines like cognitive science, psychology, engineering, robotics, computer science, social sciences and artificial intelligence. Each of these disciplines offers different viewpoints and methodologies to the field of research. It is therefore important that the interactive researcher should refrain from applying narrow approaches or limiting themselves to implementing specific methodologies. The challenge is to incorporate a wider perspective that defies current ways of thinking and opens up new

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interdisciplinary directions [55], innovative views [56, 57, 58, 59] and exciting frontiers that closely consider the intimate perspectives of user experience and are good for the consumer market.

However, because of the embodied character of the interaction, the activities of robots and humans have to be coordinated. This is an extremely complex process because it has to take place in human time scales, that is, in the 'now' time frame, must be in a given physical space and must be temporalized. The challenges are not only from an engineering but also from a social and communicative viewpoint. The focus should prioritize the 'human' side in the loop of human-robot interaction.

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Conflicts of Interest

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Sketch Bio

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